

ACCOUNTING AND CONTROL OF FUNDS OF THE FUND FOR THE
DEVELOPMENT OF INSTITUTIONS WITHIN THE PUBLIC SECTOR

Eshonkulov Sharofiddin Fakhriddinovich

Bank Finance Academy listener.

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Abstract. *As a result of the study of the categorization of non-budgetary funds, the formation of primary and aggregate documents, aspects related to the organization of accounting of non-budgetary funds of budgetary organizations, indicators, processes, relations, phenomena, specific parties, the article observed the presence of general aspects related to accounting and budgetary accounting. Scientific conclusions have been formulated and scientific proposals have been made to theoretically substantiate the purpose, tasks, functions, subject, objects, subjects, methods of accounting of extra-budgetary funds of budgetary organizations and to study the composition of reports on the movement of extra-budgetary funds of budgetary organizations, the procedure for their formation and presentation.*

Keywords: *external funds from the budget, savings, budget accounting, preliminary accounting, aggregate accounting, scheme of accounts, financial statements.*

In the development of the economy and the well-being of the population, not only the private sector is important, but also the budget system. The budget system serves for the purpose of fulfilling the functions of the state before society and for the purpose of providing services, stimulating, regulating and controlling the economy, and for the implementation of financing for a number of non-profit activities, such as defense, employment of the population.

When researching the directions of continuous and targeted financing of budgetary organizations, it is necessary, first of all, to focus on the structure of the country's budget system.

In our country, the state budget, state target funds and non-budgetary funds of budgetary organizations form a budget system.

The structure of non-budgetary funds of budgetary organizations includes the development fund of the budgetary organization, the fund for material incentives and development of medical organizations, non-budgetary funds of ministries, state committees and agencies, non-budgetary funds of budgetary organizations, which are formed at the expense of levied fees.

Based on the characteristics of the activities of budgetary organizations and studying the sources of their financing, we think that first of all, it is necessary to pay more attention to the formation of extra-budgetary funds in the social sphere, that is, educational and medical

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organizations, which have a large share in the structure of state budget expenditures. Because, by increasing the share of non-budgetary mabags in organizations of this area, the development of activities is achieved as a result of reducing the budget burden a little, and ensuring material interest in them based on the requirements of the market economy.

If we study budget organizations that receive funds from the state budget based on the characteristics and directions of activity, then state educational and medical organizations have the largest share in the structure of budgetary organizations.

Budgetary organizations are financed on the basis of estimates of income and expenses, which are drawn up for one fiscal year on extra-budgetary funds. Budgetary organizations have the following types of non-budgetary funds, and estimates of income and expenses are drawn up on them.

In this case, each structured estimate will consist of two parts, namely the Income (Income)s and the cost plan. The Income (Income) Plan provides a forecast for the types of income (income)expected during the financial year. As part of the cost, it is planned based on the balance of extra-budgetary funds in the personal Treasury account of budgetary organizations at the beginning of the fiscal year and the volume of funds expected to come during the fiscal year.

The implementation of estimates on non-budgetary funds of budgetary organizations will focus on the implementation of income and expenses in relation to the plan indicators in terms of the types of each type of funds. In this case, estimates of extra-budgetary funds of budgetary organizations in the Treasury are taken into account by the cash method, that is, the proceeds of funds to personal treasury accounts of organizations are taken into account as an expense, the transfer of cash funds from income and accounts.

In the case of budget organizations themselves, however, the execution of estimates is carried out based on the accounting and cash register method. In the case of extra-budgetary funds of budgetary organizations, income and associated receivables are initially recorded. Then, as a result of the receipt of receivables by personal treasury accounts, an increase in cash on extra-budgetary funds is taken into account.

The implementation of the expenditure plan for non-budgetary funds of budgetary organizations is recorded in the Treasury on the basis of the cash method in a similar way to income. That is, the expenditure of funds from the personal treasury accounts of organizations is taken into account as an expense. In budgetary organizations, however, the cost of extra-budgetary funds based on the calculation method is initially recognized and taken into account.

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The expenditure of funds from personal treasury accounts is recorded as the result of settlements with debtors and creditors, and the cash register is recognized as a cost. In this case, both in the Treasury and in budgetary organizations, the implementation of estimates is required to be carried out according to the plan. The forms of financial statements on the movement of extra-budgetary funds of budgetary organizations, the procedure for their compilation and submission, as well as the deadlines are also carried out on the basis of the procedure established by the financial authority.

The implementation of cost estimates related to the financing of a budgetary organization from the state budget is carried out on the basis of the cash register method. The funds allocated from the budget are financed in stages within the framework of the concluded cost estimate through personal treasury accounts opened in the Treasury, based on the assignment of the budget organization. The reason for being recognized as cash costs lies in the fact that the implementation of the state budget in our country is based on the cashier method. Therefore, the financing of budgetary organizations from the state budget or the payment of organizational obligations by the Treasury is taken into account in budgetary organizations as cash costs.

In the case of non-budgetary funds of budgetary organizations, it is necessary that income and expenses are accounted for by the emergence of income and expenses and their recognition, and not in close connection with the implementation of plans for income and expenses, or with changes in personal treasury accounts. In a word, income and expenses on non-budgetary funds should be taken into account based on the method of calculation in budgetary organizations. Income (revenues) from non-budgetary funds of budgetary organizations can be divided into two large groups: non-budgetary funds of budgetary organizations and income (revenues) generated from funds levied.

It is established that the movement of non-budgetary income and associated funds is taken into account on the basis of the instruction "on accounting in budgetary organizations", which divides it into the following "types:

- proceeds from calculations for special types of payments;
- receipts from the payment-contract form of training;
- funds of the budget Organization Development Fund, as well as funds of the fund for material promotion and development of medical organizations;
- other extra-budgetary funds".

Below we will consider the account of income on non-budgetary funds.

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Income is generated as a result of the implementation of calculations for education in higher education and secondary special, vocational educational institutions according to the regulation (February 26, 2013, No. 2431) on the payment-contract basis of students and students “on the payment-contract form of training in higher and secondary special, vocational educational institutions and the procedure for distributing funds from it”.

Income on the form of payment-contract of training in educational institutions should be taken into account in a manner consistent with the costs incurred monthly, regardless of whether payments on the basis of the concluded contract are made 4 times in one academic year.

Payments under the pay-contract form of training in higher and secondary specialized, vocational education institutions are divided into four during one academic year, and being allowed to pay serves to create relief for the educated. However, during the academic year, the costs associated with teaching are carried out month by month without interruption. In itself, the month-by-month implementation of expenses requires taking into account the income associated with them in a similar way. For this reason, the qataeyi nazar from the receipt of funds for income under the pay-contract form of training serves as the basis for recognition and accounting with the provision of educational services.

At the end of the last working day of the reporting quarter in budgetary organizations, funds saved on the cost estimate, income from the realization of goods (works, services) in the specialty of activities, part of the funds received from the rental of property standing on the balance sheet of the budgetary organization, funds left under budgetary organizations in the prescribed manner, income These revenues are counted as revenues of the budget organization's Development Fund.

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